

Computational reproducibility at Amsterdam UMC

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1. Introduction

The aim of this report is to provide an overview of the work undertaken to better understand and improve computational reproducibility at Amsterdam UMC. This work can be summarized according to two components: reproduction packages and community activities. Each of these are addressed in the following sections. The report then concludes with a summary and recommendations for actionable future activities.

2. Replication versus reproduction

The crisis of replication and reproducibility in medical science is well-documented ([Huber et al., 2018](#); [Aarts et al., 2015](#); [Niven et al., 2018](#)). Both are areas in need of further research and (financial) support, evidenced by research grant calls on the topic ([Open Science NL](#)). That said, there can be ambiguity and inconsistency in terminology. This confusion has been acknowledged by [the Harvard Data Science Review](#) and is evident elsewhere in academic material.¹ With that in mind, we first clarify the similarities and differences between replication and reproduction.

To replicate a study, a comparable analysis is conducted on *different input data* to assess whether the same scientific findings hold as the original study (*'different data, same analysis'*). To reproduce a study, an attempt is made to reproduce the findings (e.g., tables, figures) using the *same input data and code* (*'same data, same analysis'*). Given the strategic focus of Amsterdam UMC on [data-driven healthcare](#), when we refer to 'reproducibility' we are referring to [computational reproducibility](#) i.e., (re-)executing code to handle and analyze data.

One could conduct a replication study simply by reading a published manuscript and mimicking the same steps using different data, but in practice, manuscripts rarely provide sufficient detail for third parties to conduct an accurate replication. A well-constructed *replication package* can provide this level of detail through documentation, code, data, and/or detailed descriptions of data collection, handling and analyses. Generally speaking, replication packages are defined as consisting of the materials required to replicate the results of a research paper, while also being computationally reproducible ([Vilhuber et al., 2023](#)). Much of the confusion probably originates from combining these related but distinct activities under one umbrella.

As research support personnel that do not collect new data and have responsibilities for research software management, we focus on understanding and improving *reproducibility*. Reproduction is the first stepping stone on the journey to cumulative science knowledge, and a necessary one prior to

¹ The Open Science NL grant proposal advertisement is one such example of ambiguity.

replication ([Ziemann et al., 2023](#)). Arguably, a study that cannot be reproduced is not worthy of a replication attempt, since replication requires considerable investment in additional data collection. Determining whether the original study has been replicated would be almost impossible (or pointless) if it cannot even be reproduced.

Issues around reproducibility can originate directly from software usage and development: programming literacy, coding mistakes, version control, and documentation, among them. In creating and executing a series of *reproduction packages* across Amsterdam UMC, we expect to identify common barriers to reproducibility, and for those projects that are easily reproducible, we can identify best practices. This insight could inform the design of organization-wide guidelines, recommendations and training with the broader aim of enhancing the reproducibility of research at Amsterdam UMC.

3. Reproduction packages

Codecheck

We proposed a design of reproduction package that focused specifically on computational reproducibility. To do this, we adopted an existing framework: Codecheck ([Nüst & Eglen, 2021](#)).

Codecheck is a framework designed to enhance the computational reproducibility of academic publications by having a third party attempt to reproduce – using the same research materials – the findings of a manuscript submitted to a scientific journal. Here, we adopted the [original steps](#), slightly adjusted for the fact that our checks were orchestrated by the Research Data Management (RDM) team within Amsterdam UMC, rather than the editors of a journal. As such, the only notable deviation is that we ignored step 6, which concerns the journal publication process. Our adoption of Codecheck was undertaken with advice from [Daniel Nüst](#), one of the co-founders. He provided practical advice (e.g., how to submit a report) but we also had discussions on how Codecheck might be offered as a service within Amsterdam UMC – a particular challenge due to data rarely being openly available. We return to this later.

We adopted the following steps:

Step 1 We connected with a researcher or research group that wanted to take part in the Codecheck. Given the aims of this proposal, the research project did not need to be submitted to a journal, under review, or published. We considered projects at any stage in the research cycle, providing there were results (e.g., tables, figures) that the researchers produced using a computational workflow.

Step 2 We assigned an RDM consultant to conduct the Codecheck.

Step 3 The consultant ran the code using the materials provided by the author(s). Open materials were shared via a transfer or online repository (e.g., GitHub). In cases where the data could not be shared openly, the consultant was granted folder access (e.g., on a secure network drive on OneView)². In that case, appropriate advice was sought on whether additional permissions/consent were required for the consultant to access the data. We did not include studies that could only permit reproduction on the researcher's own machine. Instead, we only included studies for which the computational workflow (i.e., data, code) could be shared for execution on a *different* machine. We considered this to be a higher bar to pass for a reproducibility check, since many issues can arise from differences between researchers' computing environments (e.g., software versions). If the consultant had any issues running the code, then they requested further clarification, help, or

² OneView is a virtual desktop environment for Amsterdam UMC researchers based on [Citrix XenDesktop](#).

documentation from the author. If the author allowed it, the consultant improved or fixed issues themselves, tracking changes with version control. Git is currently not available within OneView, so projects hosted there could not be tracked with version control. As per the guidelines, we iterated this process until the consultant could successfully reproduce the paper’s findings, or the consultant concluded that the findings were not reproducible ([Nüst & Eglen, 2021; p4](#)).

Step 4 The consultant wrote a short final report detailing how the check was conducted, the results of the check, a list of the changes made, and any recommendations for the researcher(s).

Step 5 The report was archived on [Zenodo](#) and given a citable Digital Object Identifier (DOI) alongside other Codecheck reports conducted internationally. After consultation with the Codecheck founders, we concluded that for now only those checks using open data and open code would be archived in the official Codecheck repository.

Codecheck projects

Projects were largely identified through community meet-ups, such as the [R User Group at Amsterdam UMC](#) (RUM-UMC, see later section) or through direct recommendations from colleagues. The initial experience of contacting researchers, explaining what a Codecheck entails, and inviting them to take part, already provided some useful insight. More often than not, researchers were enthusiastic about the idea of a Codecheck, but declined, recommending a colleague’s project instead, or postponed the offer for a future project. In many cases researchers were worried about the prospect of ‘failing’ the Codecheck (i.e., that the codechecker from RDM would not be able to reproduce their findings). This made it difficult to recruit volunteers.

At the time of writing, four Codechecks have been completed, summarized in Table 1. Projects 1 and 3 used open data and open code, and so the final report could be published on the official Codecheck Zenodo page with a corresponding GitHub repository. The final report for Project 2 was published on OSF by the author because the data was sensitive and not openly available (the report also had to be anonymized for peer-review). At the time of writing, Project 4 is complete, but we are awaiting final confirmation from the authors before publication on Zenodo. Project 5 is ongoing but preliminary feedback has been provided. All projects used R as the primary programming language.

Table 1 Codecheck projects completed.

ID	Researcher	Department	Language	Open data	Open code	Codecheck report
1	Ayu Dewi	Epidemiology & Data Science	R	Yes	Yes	Zenodo
2	Daan Toben	Public and Occupational Health	R	No	Yes	OSF
3	Jeroen Hoogland	Epidemiology & Data Science	R	Yes	Yes	Zenodo
4	Rodrigo Garcia Valentia	Epidemiology & Data Science	R	Yes	Yes	SharePoint
5	Merel Postema	Neuroscience / Research Data Management	R	No	No	In progress

Findings

All four completed projects in Table 1 received a Codecheck certificate. The Codecheck certificates themselves, referenced in Table 1, provide case-by-case details. The ease and speed with which projects were reproduced varied considerably. The experience ranged from results being reproduced within a matter of minutes, without any additional advice from the researcher(s), to requiring input from the researcher(s) via emails and in-person meetings to clarify ambiguities and understand errors in the code. Here, we do not refer to projects individually, but rather, summarize the experience via a series of recommendations according to three components: documentation, work spaces, and projects/virtual environments. We would emphasize that these recommendations are not exhaustive, but rather, they are simple and realistic things that researchers can implement easily, and by doing so, increase the likelihood of reproducibility by a third party.

Documentation

- Computational workflow packages, even if only comprised of one or two scripts, should state (1) which scripts need executing and (2) in what order the scripts need executing. Ideally, the scripts are also named according to this order (e.g., 1_data_handling.R) for clarification and ease of use. This is a simple addition that is often overlooked. Best practice advice in [existing RDM courses](#) does already reflect this recommendation.
- When using git, extra care is required when working with empty folders. By default, empty folders will not be pushed to the remote repository, even if they exist on the researcher's machine. Anyone pulling the remote to their own machine will not have these folders and this will cause issues with running the code (issues that can be masked with unclear error messages, and therefore difficult to diagnose). Adding a readme.txt (or equivalent) to the folder is one way of solving this problem. Alternatively, one could automate this process by adding an installation script that creates the folder or via a git post-checkout hook ([Ponuthorai & Loeliger, 2022, p349](#)).

Workspaces

- In alignment with more official recommendations ([Wickham & Golemund, 2017](#)), researchers should not use 'workspaces' within RStudio. Saving a workspace will generate an .RData file containing all the objects in a researcher's current Global Environment. Using workspaces can easily lead to confusion about how and when objects were created and can result in scripts referring to objects that do not exist. This is not just a problem for reproducibility, but also the *regeneration* of results by the researchers themselves. These problems can be avoided by changing the default settings in RStudio. The workspace should not be preserved between sessions, and to avoid unintentionally saving one, the 'never' option should be selected for saving upon exit (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 Turning off workspaces in RStudio 2024.09.1.

Projects and virtual environments

- Researchers should work within *R project* files (.Rproj) located in the root folder of the research project itself. This helps avoid issues originating from absolute/unique/personal working directories. That said, it doesn't remove these issues automatically: setting absolute working directories is still possible when using R project files. Working within an .Rproj file just makes it easier *not* to rely on them. Our advice would be to never set or change the working directory unless absolutely necessary, but instead, use .Rproj files in the root folder of each distinct research project.
- Researchers working with a different IDE or standalone R can still have the benefits of .Rproj files by using relative working directories, but these need to be carefully incorporated into the script to ensure that code can be executed on other machines. That said, given the availability of RStudio within OneView, and its popularity with the R community in general, the usage of .Rproj files can be widely and easily implemented within Amsterdam UMC.
- When creating .Rproj files, researchers should also activate a virtual environment using the renv package. This has become a standard practice within R and has now been integrated into the RStudio IDE as a tickbox when creating .Rproj files. Researchers can also do this retrospectively using renv functions. Using such a virtual environment helps researchers easily document and manage their R and package versions, and allows third parties to quickly restore the researcher's original R environment.
- There is a known problem with using renv within OneView that causes RStudio to crash.³ At the time of writing, the recommendation is to not initiate the virtual environment using `renv::init()` because this is the action that causes the crash. Instead, researchers can take a snapshot of their environment using `renv::snapshot()` without initializing the virtual environment, and in doing so, create a lockfile that can be restored by a third party. Alternatively, researchers can save a text file or .RData object containing the session information generated from `sessionInfo()`.
- Arguably, renv or saving session information is more easily actionable than using [Docker](#) or other equivalent containers. This is a balance between best practices and providing solutions that researchers can and will implement.

³ The issue has been raised with ICT (see ticket INC0751524) and discussed with colleagues in RDM, but no long-term fix has been proposed that would permit full usage of renv within OneView.

As a more general remark, common errors encountered (e.g., objects not found, using working directories that no longer exist, functions not recognized due to unloaded packages) demonstrated that the researchers themselves did not always execute their computational workflows from start to finish at the close of the project (i.e., they had not regenerated their own findings, on their own machine). Or, they *thought* they had regenerated the computational workflow from start to finish, but due to the unintentional usage of workspaces, the issues are not encountered, and therefore problems never uncovered until a reproduction attempt by a third party. Some of the barriers to reproducibility encountered here could be avoided pre-Codecheck simply by the researcher attempting a full regeneration of their own findings after restarting R and clearing their Global Environment.

Future plans

The Codecheck reports were a useful experience for the researchers: they received feedback on their work and a citable report that helped with the peer-review process and final publication.⁴ It was also a valuable experience for the research software consultants: the process provided insight into the research software practices of researchers, including barriers to reproducibility. There is prospect for Codechecks to become integrated into the support services of RDM. One proposal would be to offer Codechecks within the ServiceNow system. This way, researchers could independently request one, a ticket would be generated and an RDM consultant/advisor assigned. At the time of writing, RDM plans to offer Codechecks as a pilot service.

For the pilot and/or long-term services, we might want to rename ‘Codechecks’ to ‘reproducibility checks’ (or similar) to avoid confusion with other forms of advice, such as statistical support or coding support (e.g., to reduce computation time). A key way of promoting this service, while encouraging best practices, would be to incorporate the reproducibility check into the existing DMP plan. For instance: “Analysis scripts will be re-executed by a third party to ensure that the main results are reproducible [tick box]”). This wording gives the researchers flexibility to ask a colleague to conduct the check informally, but an additional comment can be added for those wanting independent support, containing a link to ServiceNow. For instance: “You can request an independent reproducibility check from the Research Data Management team [link here]”. An alternative home for these additions might be the Statistical Analysis Plan.

Here, we would emphasize that the Codecheck framework was originally adopted as a guide for completing reproducibility packages. There is no obligation to continue following Codecheck guidelines for internal reproducibility checks. There are benefits for continuing the link, namely, that Codecheck already has working processes such as a template report, support from the co-founders and a Zenodo repository for citable reports. It also has an international reach and a (growing) reputation, with active participants from other universities that standardize the reproducibility check process.

A reason to abandon the official Codecheck framework in favor of something tailored for Amsterdam UMC would be because, by default, official Codechecks must have open data and open code. Many (likely, the majority) of code-based projects at Amsterdam UMC use data that cannot be made publicly available. That said, at the time of writing, our pre-existing usage of [DataverseNL](#) might be sufficient for Codechecks, because third parties can openly view the metadata and request access to the raw data (even though being granted access is not guaranteed). In such cases, the code should still be made available, ideally under version control via GitHub. These discussions are ongoing within the Codecheck community.

⁴ Testimonials were collected for potential advertisements in the future (see [SharePoint](#)).

Whatever we choose in the future, researchers should at the bare minimum provide the following research materials and metadata during their request for a Codecheck:

- The manuscript containing the results that will be reproduced. This is so that the Codechecker can make the comparison to assess whether the results have been reproduced (or not).
- By default, it is assumed that the scripts will produce all the results in the manuscript. If this is not the case, the researcher should list the results (i.e., tables and figures) that the scripts will (not) reproduce.
- If not contained in the manuscript (e.g., due to anonymity) the list of authors and their corresponding affiliations.
- Any data required for the scripts to be executed.

There are additional actions and materials, partially aligned with the recommendations outlined earlier, that would make the Codecheck process more efficient for RDM to conduct. These could be requested or stated as a 'to do' list prior to requesting a Codecheck on ServiceNow. As with other aspects of this report, these recommendations are a balance between the ideal best practices and what is feasible and realistic to request of researchers that have limited time.

- Instructions on how to run the scripts (e.g., in what order).
- Either (1) a renv environment with an up-to-date lock file, or (2) a text file or .RData object containing the output from `sessionInfo()`. Option 1 is preferable.
- The researcher should ensure that they themselves, on their own machine, can execute the entire computational workflow from start to finish, having restarted R and cleared the Global Environment.
- The researcher should specify any dependencies not captured by the packaging of the software they provide (e.g., Operating System-level dependencies not captured by renv).
- The researcher should specify computational requirements such as the number of CPU and GPU cycles, as well as memory requirements, if they go beyond a standard laptop.

4. Community activities

A number of community activities, typically focused around knowledge sharing and training around reproducibility, were carried out during the project: a reproducibility hackathon, the founding and hosting of an R user group, a pilot workshop on version control using GitHub Desktop, and a poster presentation at the Dutch Reproducibility Network.

Reproducibility hackathon

The reproducibility hackathon was co-organized with doctoral students from the Department of Neuroscience. The main contribution from RDM was the opportunity to present about reproducible workflows in R ([source material on GitHub](#)). This included some of the recommendations outlined above, such as using virtual environments. It was clear that, even among the attendees who were a self-selected group of R or Python enthusiasts, many best practices were not routinely being followed within neuroscience. This was further evidenced by the hackathon itself, in which small groups attempted to reproduce the published research results of colleagues (see [hack md doc](#)). In almost all cases, attendees had issues (easily) reproducing the study's results. Many of the issues, [summarized in the hack md doc](#), were familiar: projects had no session information or virtual environments, functions were used from non-loaded packages, objects were not found, and/or instructions were lacking on how to execute scripts. The findings from the reproducibility hackathon aligned clearly with the findings from the Codechecks.

R user meet-ups

In June 2024, the first R user meet-up for Amsterdam UMC (RUM-UMC) was held. Prior to that, there was no active, cross-departmental R user group at the organization. Since then, we have hosted 14 workshops on MS Teams, reached 72 unique attendees, and have had a (rounded) mean attendance of 15 people. Topics have included data visualization, data handling (e.g., dates), unit tests, spatial data, building websites, version control, making reports using Quarto, RShiny, and general tips on reproducibility. The schedule and session materials can be found on [the website](#). Topics were largely determined by the availability of speakers and their corresponding expertise. Session five, on reproducibility, was directly informed by the experience of the Codechecks and the reproducibility hackathon. That session was updated and repeated for the [R café at TU Delft](#).

Figure 2 Attendance of RUM-UMC sessions over time.

GitHub workshop

Following a personal request, and in alignment with the organization-wide plan to adopt and support GitHub Enterprise (see [Pronk & Geertsma, 2024](#)), a pilot workshop was designed and given to the Department of Psychiatry on GitHub Desktop. The [source material](#), [slides](#), and [worksheet](#) are openly available for reuse and amendments by colleagues or other institutions. Approximately 15 researchers attended from the Department, most of which were doctoral students, although at least one decentral data manager attended. We did not collect feedback systematically, but the verbal and email comments after the workshop were positive. A [compressed version of the session](#) was re-run for RUM-UMC.

The decision to teach GitHub Desktop, rather than say the git Command-Line Interface (CLI), was based on a balance between the needs of researchers and usability/accessibility. The cumulative experience of the activities presented in this report confirmed that researchers at Amsterdam UMC tend not to require the advanced functionality of git. Rather, they only require functions to put their analysis pipelines under version control, and in some cases, collaborate with colleagues via the remote. Those that *do* require the advanced functionality of git tend to already have that experience. It was therefore difficult to justify the increased difficulty, and corresponding increased likelihood of usage drop-off after a course, that you can get with git CLI, that we have experienced first-hand when helping to teach [Software Carpentry sessions at the VU](#). Even with just this one-hour workshop in GitHub Desktop, students were able to

perform basic git functions that could be immediately applied to their analysis pipelines. That said, we would need a follow-up survey to determine what proportion of attendees continued to use it.

Dutch reproducibility network

As part of the Dutch Reproducibility Network (NLRN), we presented an overview of related activities in a poster entitled *Improving Computational Reproducibility at Amsterdam UMC*. It was subsequently published on Zenodo ([Bocancea et al., 2024](#)). The poster was created and presented together with the organizing committee from the Reproducibility Hackathon. This was an opportunity to promote and discuss our activities with researchers and research support staff from universities and UMCs across the Netherlands. One of the main talking points was Codechecks. A number of universities were conducting Codechecks, with the Erasmus School of Social and Behavioural Sciences already piloting Codecheck as a support service that researchers could request. At the time, there was low demand for this service. Two potential sources of this low demand were discussed. First, the labelling of the service as a ‘Codecheck’ might be misleading. By name, it does not imply ‘reproducibility’ and may even deter researchers who are running basic analysis scripts, because they do not consider their work to be ‘coding’. Second, even if researchers fully understand what service is being offered, there is no incentive for them to volunteer for a reproducibility check. It is rarely a requirement for grants or publications (two key activities and pressures for researchers) and, as we experienced within Amsterdam UMC, researchers are worried about ‘failing’ and jeopardizing publications. This challenge could be addressed partly through the labelling and advertising of the service: not as a ‘test’ that can be passed or failed, but rather, as a support service for which the principal aim is to provide feedback to the researcher.

5. Conclusion

Summary

Two main activities have been undertaken to better understand and improve computational reproducibility at Amsterdam UMC, namely, producing a series of reproduction packages and undertaking community activities. The reproduction packages were created in alignment with the Codecheck framework ([Nüst & Eglén, 2021](#)). To date, four packages have been completed, in the form of a Codecheck report, and one is ongoing. The process of conducting the Codechecks provided valuable insight for RDM but also provided targeted and actionable feedback for researchers. Based on this experience, Codecheck ‘reproducibility checks’ will be offered as a pilot service by RDM.

Community activities included the founding and running of a reproducibility hackathon, an R user group, a one-off workshop on GitHub Desktop, and a presentation at NLRN. These activities were a useful method for gaining information about common software practices and barriers to reproducibility at Amsterdam UMC, but also a channel for disseminating knowledge and promoting best practices in software usage and management.

Recommendations

A number of recommendations can be made based on the experiences outlined in these report.

1. Host – or assist departments in the hosting of – reproducibility hackathons.
2. Pilot Codecheck as an RDM service. As outlined above, this recommendation has already been actioned.
3. Make additions to the DMP and/or SAP to promote reproducibility checks. This could happen in three ways, namely:

- a. Add a tick box to encourage researchers to execute their entire computational workflows from start to finish before archiving their data and code. This is more ‘regeneration’ but it feeds directly into reproducibility.
 - b. Offering Codecheck as a service.
 - c. Encouraging peer-to-peer reproducibility checks i.e., doctoral students ask one another to conduct a reproducibility check on their own work. This could also be the basis for the reproducibility hackathon.
4. Collaborate further with initiatives for further standardizing the way research objects are organized, such as ENCORE ([van Kampen et al., 2024](#)) and [RO-Crate \(Soiland-Reyes et al., 2022\)](#), to establish whether reproducibility checks can be automated, given a standardized folder structure.
 5. Continuation of the R user group (RUM-UMC). Based on the consistent attendance, this is a valuable service that RDM can offer to promote research software best practices, and in turn, enhance reproducibility. It also helps RDM keep their ‘ear to ground’ with regards to understanding current issues and training demands. At the time of writing, RUM-UMC will be continued.
 6. As part of LDCC-3, ensure that new training materials include GitHub (Desktop) and reproducibility as topics.
 - a. GitHub Desktop. The materials for [the existing workshop](#) could be reused or adapted for this.
 - b. Reproducibility. A standard course for all students to clarify terminology and demonstrate how pervasive the problem is within medical research (i.e., it is the norm for studies not to be reproducible, not the exception). After that, there could then be language-specific courses for R and Python giving practical, hands-on advice. Here, a mini reproducibility hackathon might be useful, because students then see for themselves how difficult it is to reproduce someone else’s work. We can also draw inspiration from courses developed at other universities in the Netherlands, such as [one on publication packages at Erasmus University Rotterdam](#).

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